

REPORT:

TESTS PERFORMED ON A REINFORCED SCALE ROCKFALL EMBANKMENT LOADED IN A QUASI-STATIC MODE

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The coordination of the tests was overseen by Daniele Peila and Valerio De Biagi (critical mass staff from NODES).

The people involved to carry out the test campaigns were:

- Test n°1: Stefano Vigna, Maddalena Marchelli, Simone Saltarin, Andrea Carigi, Vincenzo Di Pietra, Nives Grasso, Diego Franco, Daniele Peila, Valerio De Biagi.
- Test n°2: Stefano Vigna, Maddalena Marchelli, Simone Saltarin, Andrea Carigi, Carmine Todaro, Alfio Di Giovanni, Vincenzo Di Pietra, Daniele Peila, Valerio De Biagi.

OBJECTIVE

The tests aimed to reproduce and analyze the instant of collapse of a reinforced rockfall protection embankment (RE-RPE). Specifically, the goal was to identify the geometric configuration that precedes the collapse condition through scaled tests.

Two experimental campaigns were conducted: the first between 4-6 September 2023, and the second between 10-12 October 2023.

SCALING LAW

The RPE was constructed at a reduced scale to facilitate the construction procedures. The scaling law was derived using the Pi theorem. Five fundamental quantities were selected, which depend on three units of measurement; hence, the 5-3 Pi terms were defined as fundamental for describing the problem:

$$\pi_1 = \frac{a \cdot \rho \cdot l^3}{F} = [-] \quad \pi_2 = \varepsilon = [-]$$

Given the scaling factors of the fundamental quantities λ^i , the scaling factors of the other variables λ were derived accordingly:

Fundamental quantities	Scale factor	Derivative quantities	Scale factor
Length l	λ	Mass m	λ^3
Acceleration a	1	Time t	$\lambda^{1/2}$
Density ρ	1	Velocity v	$\lambda^{1/2}$
Force F	λ^3	Pressure p	1
Strain ε	1	Stress σ	1
		Ultimate stress of the reinforcement T_{max}	λ^2

From a practical standpoint, the actual implementation of the scaling law is constrained by the inability to scale gravity and by the fact that the ultimate strength of the available scaled reinforcement is limited to commercially available products.

MATERIALS USED AND GEOMETRIES

Materials used for the reinforcement

Different force-deformation curves on meshes easily available on the market were measured to construct an appropriate scaling law.

For the first experimental campaign, a double-twist hexagonal gardening mesh (13x13 mm with \varnothing 0.7 mm) was used. A tensile test was performed on its according to the UNI EN 10223-3 standard (with dimensions of 100x80 mm and \varnothing 2.2 mm), adapting the machine setup to the specimen size. The configuration of the test is shown in Figure 1a. To obtain representative values, ten tensile tests were conducted (see curves in Figure 2a and Table 1). The average tensile strength allows to fix $\lambda = 3.3$.

Subsequently, for the second experimental campaign, we wanted to reduce the scale factor to $\lambda = 5$. Therefore, a 15x15 mm PP mesh (called “rete avicola”) was used to simulate the Terramesh system of Maccaferri (Figure 1b). Ten tensile tests were repeated to obtain statistically representative resistance values (see curves in Figure 2b and Table 1).

The results of the ten tensile tests for both materials were purified by removing the maximum and minimum resistance values to obtain a representative average value. The average values are reported in Table 1.

Figure 1: [a] Tensile test on hexagonal double-twist net; [b] Tensile test on poultry net.

[a]

[b]

Figure 2: Tensile test curves.

Table 1: Tensile test results.

MATERIAL: Hexagonal DT mesh	F_{max} [kN/m]	ϵ_{max} [-]
Test 1	11.88	0.223
Test 2	13.15	0.226
Test 3	10.26	0.244
Test 4	12.12	0.221
Test 5	13.57	0.197
Test 7	5.91	0.081
Test 8	12.86	0.210
Test 9	12.05	0.185
Test 10	10.39	0.199
Test 11	11.51	0.233

Assumed value	11.78	0.218
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MATERIAL: Rete Avicola	F_{max} [kN/m]	ϵ_{max} [-]
Test 11	1.207	0.30499
Test 12	1.489	0.164188
Test 13	1.423	0.175554
Test 14	1.470	0.152815
Test 15	1.362	0.136101
Test 16	1.263	0.11801
Test 17	0.973	0.216527
Test 18	1.366	0.111786
Test 19	0.959	0.112985
Test 20	1.158	0.152918

Assumed value	1.52	0.171
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Filling Material: Soil

The soil used as filling material was characterized through grain size analysis and Proctor compaction tests. The results are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Soil characterization.

During the construction phases, as described below, an in-situ compaction test was conducted using the sand cone method in accordance with ASTM D 1556-90. This test established that with four passes of a vibrating plate per layer, a compaction level greater than 95% of the optimal Proctor density is achieved.

Additionally, a plate load test was performed on one layer in accordance with CNR BU 146/92. The setup of the test and the pressure on the plate (P) versus the average recorded settlements (δ) are shown in Figure 4, while the numerical values are presented in Table 2. These values allow for the determination of a deformation modulus $M_d = 24.2$ MPa, in accordance with the standard.

Table 2: Recorded pressure and settlement values.

	P [MPa]	δ [mm]	$\delta - \delta_{precarico}$ [mm]
Pre-load	0.0201	0.0489	0.0000
Load 1	0.0515	0.3974	0.3485
Load 2	0.1027	1.0271	0.9782
Load 3	0.1512	1.6316	1.5827
Load 4	0.2037	2.3640	2.3151

[a]

[b]

Figure 4: Plate load tests conducted.

Test Setup

Experimental campaign n°1 utilized a scaling factor of $\lambda = 3.3$, with the cross-section of the constructed embankment shown in Figure 5.

Experimental campaign n°2 used a scaling factor of $\lambda = 5$, with the cross-section of the constructed embankments illustrated in Figure 6.

Table 3 presents the main real and reproduced quantities from the prototypes constructed according to the scaling law. In the case of the second experimental campaign, the ultimate strength of the reinforcement of 40 kN/m is intended to represent the hexagonal double-twist mesh product “Green Terramesh Light,” manufactured by Maccaferri, type 8x10 (EN 10223-3) with diameters of 2.20/3.2 mm.

Table 3: Main scaled quantities in the two experimental campaigns.

Features	Experimental campain n°1		Experimental campain n°2	
	Real	$\lambda=3.3$	Real	$\lambda=5$
Side slope	67°	67°	67°	67°
RE-RPE crest	1.5 m	0.45 m	2 m	0.40 m
RPE height	0.76 m	0.23 m	0.76 m	0.15 m
N° of layers	8	8	8	8
Ultimate tensile strenght	$128 \frac{kN}{m}$	$11.78 \frac{kN}{m}$	$\approx 40 \frac{kN}{m}$	$1.52 \frac{kN}{m}$

Figure 5: Cross-section of the embankment at a scale of $\lambda = 3.3$.

Figure 6: Cross-section of the embankment at a scale of $\lambda = 5$.

CONSTRUCTION OF THE EMBANKMENTS AND THE TEST FIELD

Experimental campaign n°1, $\lambda=3.3$

The RE-RPE was constructed by confining it between two walls made of concrete blocks (Figure 7a). The cross-section was marked on them, and eight layers were formed using wooden plank formwork (Figure 7d). The formwork was removed at the end of each layer construction. Each layer of soil is wrapped in the scaled reinforcement mesh and has a length of overlap of 50-60 cm. The mesh panels were overlapped and tied in these zones to ensure adequate structural continuity (Figure 7b). Furthermore, between each layer, metal clips were installed as the Terramesh system of Maccaferri recommend.

After laying the mesh and formwork, soil was inserted and compacted using a manual vibrating plate (Figure 7d). A compaction test was performed on the first layer: after four passes of the plate, an in-situ density test was conducted using the sand cone method (Figure 7c), which confirmed that this number of passes is sufficient to exceed 95% of the Proctor density. Consequently, all subsequent layers were compacted using this methodology.

Figure 7e shows the completed realization of the embankment and the set up to recorder the displacements on the down-stream side bank. Two movable bar frames were installed to measure displacements, and a beam was placed on top, onto which LVDT sensors were attached to measure vertical displacements on the crest. Markers were applied on the down-stream bank for continuous monitoring of displacements through a photogrammetry network. Finally, an optical fiber was installed at a point on the fifth layer of mesh to verify the feasibility of measuring the strain state of the mesh with this technique.

As visible in Figure 7e, the final result of the obtained profile is not perfect, and the geometry achieved does not perfectly match the design: the crest is approximately 70-80 cm wide and has a total height of about 1.90 m.

The construction phase took place on 4-6/06/2023.

[a]

[b]

[c]

[d]

[e]

Figure 7: Construction phases of the RPE with $\lambda = 3.3$.

Experimental campaign n°2, $\lambda=5$

The construction followed the same steps described in the previous chapter, with the following improvements:

- A non-woven geotextile (100 g/m²) was inserted on the bank parts of each layer to retain the fine material.
- The system in Figures 8a-b-c was used to obtain the correct cross section of the structures.

As shown in the final construction in Figure 8f, two geometrically equivalent embankments were created. One was equipped with clips connecting (as Terramesh system recommend) between the two adjacent reinforcement layers; for each layer, two rows of ties were installed at intervals of about 5 cm, while the other embankment was constructed without clips.

The construction phase took place on 16-18/10/2023.

Figure 8: Construction phases of the RPE with $\lambda = 5$.

EXECUTION OF THE TESTS

Experimental campaign n°1, $\lambda=3.3$

The embankment was subjected to loading using a punch that simulates the impact of a falling block. The punch consists of a metal plate with a diameter of 30 cm, which was applied in a quasi-static manner to the 6th and 7th layers of the RPE. As shown in the diagram in Figure 5, the force was applied using a hydraulic jack resting on a counteracting medium (excavator). The advantage of this method is the ability to maintain a continuous load and to measure the force applied by the jack through a pressure transducer connected to the jack pump.

However, the available jack has a limited stroke of about 10 cm, which proved insufficient to perform the test as planned. The initial phase of loading, which only utilized the stroke of the jack, is visible in Figure 9a. Figure 9b shows how the plate became completely embedded in the embankment when the jack was released. Subsequently, the stroke of the jack was extended using a wooden wedge (Figure 9c), and finally, collapse was reached by pushing the jack and wedge assembly with the movement of the excavator (Figure 9d). The configuration considered immediately before collapse is shown in Figures 10 and 11.

The pre-collapse configuration was identified when, due to excessive deformation, the reinforcement was no longer able to contain the soil. Thus, any further displacement of the punch would result in the total collapse of the affected area. To confirm this, a small increment of displacement was applied to the punch using the movement of the excavator, resulting in the collapse shown in Figure 12.

The pressure recorded on the jack during the test execution is presented in the graph of Figure 13, where a phase of constant pressure is observed between 500 s and 700 s, approximately 75 bar, which is interpreted as

the pressure necessary for the observed kinematics to occur. The subsequent peaks are attributed to the jack's bottom stroke and should therefore not be considered.

The sensors positioned at the crest proved ineffective, as the kinematics caused significant downward displacements of the instrumented section.

Figure 9: Execution phases leading to the collapse of the embankment viewed from above.

Figure 10: Pre-collapse configuration: [a] View from the Mountain side; [b] View from the valley side.

[a]

[b]

Figure 11: Pre-collapse configuration with detail on the panel ties: [a] view from the valley side; [b] view from the mountain side.

[a]

[b]

Figura 12: Collapse configuration: [a] view from the mountain side; [b] view from the valley side.

Figura 13: Pressure recorded on the jack during the test for $\lambda = 3.3$.

Experimental campaign n°2, $\lambda=5$

The principle and purposes are the same as in the previously described case; however, the push system was obtained using a jack that allowed for continued loading until collapse was implemented, as depicted in Figure 14. A 20-ton long-stroke hydraulic jack (maximum stroke of 38 cm) was installed horizontally on a concrete block, and its maximum stroke was further extended using custom-made extensions (Figure 14b).

Therefore, the loading was continuous until collapse was achieved, and it was interrupted only during the installation phases of the extensions. The loading was applied to a metal plate with a diameter of 30 cm and at a height between the 4th and 5th layers in both cases.

Figure 14: Push system built for the second experimental campaign.

Figures 15 and 16 show the pre-collapse condition for the embankment without clips and with clips, respectively. In the first case, it can be observed that the resisting behavior predominantly involves only the layers subjected to loading, specifically the 5th and 6th layers, while the upper layers remain relatively

undistorted. In contrast, for the case with clips, the reinforced embankment reacts with the involvement of the upper layers as well, namely the 7th and 8th layers, which are completely engaged in the kinematic behavior.

Additionally, the cracking pattern formed at the crest is markedly different in the two scenarios: Figure 17 illustrates how, in the case without ties, "tension cracks" form longitudinally along the embankment, whereas in the case with ties, the "tension cracks" result in a distinct cone of diffusion at approximately 45°.

The graph in Figure 18 displays the pressures recorded on the jack in both cases. Constant pressure plateaus are observed, which do not significantly differ in magnitude between the cases with and without clips, interspersed with moments of release corresponding to the operational times for mounting the extensions.

Figure 15: Case WITHOUT TIES: pre-collapse situation viewed from the mountain side [a] and valley side [b].

Figure 16: Case WITH TIES: pre-collapse situation viewed from the mountain side [a] and valley side [b].

[a]

[b]

Figure 17: Cracking pattern at the crest in the case WITHOUT TIES [a] and WITH TIES [b].

Figure 18: Pressure recorded on the jack during the test for the case $\lambda=5$.

CONCLUSIONS

The collapse kinematics observed with the quasi-static load appears to be heavily influenced by the presence of ties. Moreover, the case without ties closely resembles the dynamic conditions observed in Peila et al. (2007) experimental campaign (Figures 15). In both cases with incorporated clips, despite the different scale factor and type of reinforcement, the resulting collapse mechanism seems to align (Figures 10 and 16).

The influence of clips between the layers of the mesh significantly affects the number of layers involved in the kinematics. In contrast to the embankments tested by Peila et al. (2007), no sliding of solely the involved layers is observed. In the case of $\lambda=3.3$, both the upper and lower layers (the 5th and 8th from the bottom) are involved in the kinematics, even though they are not directly affected by the plate. In the case of $\lambda=5$, all layers up to the top participate in the kinematics.

A careful evaluation of the photogrammetric surveys carried out and currently being processed will allow for a clearer definition of the structure's collapse. These surveys are presently the subject of numerical back-analysis to find a correlation between the geometry of the RPE, the lengths of the overlaps, and the impact height.